

TRADE RELATIONS BETWEEN KOKAND KHANATE AND EASTERN TURKEY

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Аннотация: В статье представлены сведения о торгово-экономических связях Кокандского ханства с Восточным Туркестаном. В частности, были высказаны научные взгляды на усиление экономического влияния Кокандского ханства в Восточно- Туркестанской области, оккупированной китайско-маньчжурским правительством.

Ключевые слова: Кокандское ханство, Восточный Туркестан, китайско-маньчжурское правление, «андижанцы», уйгуры, Синьцзян, Ганьсу.

Annotation: The article provides information on the connections of Kokand's Khanate conducting trade economic trends with East Turkestan. In particular, the Chinese Turkestan province has made researchers to strengthen the economic impact of the Kokand Khanate.

Keywords: Kokand khanate, East Turkistan, China-Manjur Government, Uyghurs, Xinjong, Gansu.

The rulers of Kokand tried to spend all their domestic and foreign policies on the development of the country. During the years of strong centralization of the state, there was a revival in the economy and cultural life of the country. The foreign economic relations of the Kokand Khanate played an important role in the growth of the country's economy. In particular, trade with East Turkestan (which the Chinese called Xinjong, meaning "New Country"), which was occupied by China during 1755-1759, was important for the khanate's economy. The activities of Central Asian traders and artisans, including citizens of the Kokand Khanate, were considered important in this trade. In Central Asian sources of the 18th and 19th centuries and in Chinese documents, they were known as "Andijan people." The study of their activities opens new pages in the history of Uzbekistan.

The main trade route between Andijan and Kashgar-Khotan, which connects China with Central Asia and Russia and the Middle East, passes through the Osh-SufikorovulTerak Pass-Twin, which is considered the safest and closest route for traders. In turn, Central Asian traders also entered Chinese territory through the cities of East Turkestan. In the 17th century, Chinese documents confirm that Fergana traders traded in Gansu Province, China [2.S.225]. Russian orientalist V. V. Describing Andijan and the "Andijan people", Barthold wrote: "Trade relations between Central Asia and East Turkestan were carried out through" Andijan "traders.

On the other hand, Andijan became so popular that even other traders and artisans from all over Central Asia were called "Andijan people" in the Uyghur land "[1. S.326]. Therefore, it was not in vain that several addresses in East Turkestan were called by the same name. In particular, one of the streets of the Yangikurgan district, built in 1838 by the governor of Kashgar Zuhiriddinbek, is Andijan Street, Andijan Palace, the largest caravanserai in the center of Kashgar, and the address of Little Andijan near Kashgar.

The peoples of Central Asia (primarily the Fergana Valley) and East Turkestan have long coexisted as part of a single ethnocultural and historical state. The Uyghurs of East Turkestan and the Uzbeks of Fergana spoke a close dialect and had no difficulty in trade or commerce. As a result of the arrival of many people in East Turkestan in the Fergana Valley and the migration of Uzbeks to East Turkestan, economic and trade relations between Uzbeks and Uighurs were established. Therefore, they also had a social life and a mutual marital relationship. The settlers of the khanate were mainly merchants and artisans, and some of them were engaged in agriculture and animal husbandry. The majority of the population in these two areas is Muslim, and trade was largely based on Sharia law. From the above, it is clear that there are interdependencies and similarities in the socio-economic and cultural life of the people of these two regions. The migration of the population to one region or another due to political processes has also accelerated trade relations.

The Kokand rulers tried to keep the Kokand traders in Shingjong under their control. To do this, he appointed an elder from among them. Opinions also differ as to which Kokand ruler was first appointed by this elder. The Uyghur historian Qurban Ali Ayaguzi believed that this system of elders was established after the 1832 Kokand-China agreement. But in our opinion, the position of God existed even before the Norbutabi period, and was a career elected by the people, controlling the markets. This position is similar to that of a market elder who controlled the markets in the Central Asian khanates. In particular, he was the elder of the Margilan market, who opened the market with a "blessing" and controlled the market. He prevented unscrupulous acts such as deception of buyers by market vendors, sale of low quality goods and theft. But the powers of the market elder in Xingjong were broad, strengthening relations between the Sino-Manchu government and the Kokand Khanate. He controlled the Kokand people in Xingjong according to Sharia law, collected taxes from them and sent them to the Kokand ruler, controlled the Kokand coins circulating in the Shingjong markets, and protected the Kokand people from Chinese-Manchurian and local officials.

So, after the Chinese-Manchurian government allowed Kokand traders to trade in Xinjong markets, they entered Xinjiang and expanded their trading activities in the country.

Kashgar is one of the largest trade centers of East Turkestan, where Kokand traders operated, and it has long been a major intermediary of Central Asian goods and a center for the supply of Chinese goods to the East. The traders who came here took their goods to other cities of East Turkestan: Yorkend, Yangihisar, Khotan, Aksu, Uchturfon. The center has full facilities for traders. In particular, in the middle of the XIX century in Kashgar there were more than 30 caravanserais. Merchants from Kokand and Andijan mostly settled in the Andijansaroy caravanserai of the city, while traders from Margilan stayed more in the caravanserai named after Konaksaray [5.S.90].

One of the centers where Kokand traders are active -

It was Uchturfon. A Chinese document states that "traders from Andijan were allowed to graze their cattle on pastures near Osh (Uchturfon)." Kokand traders also began to enter Aksu through Kyrgyz lands. The city of Aksu, a major trade center, has always been open to local and foreign traders on the basis of equal privileges. With the opening of the market, people quarreled and bought goods from shops, where Kokand traders traded not only products made in the khanate, but also precious stones dug in the mountains around Hotan and Yorkend, according to a Chinese document. This shows that the Kokand traders were the leaders in trade relations in East Turkestan, where they also controlled trade with local products, which played an important role in the range of goods sold here. According to Chinese documents, "Kokand traders gradually seized the domestic markets of East Turkestan, amassed property and funds, and rented Uyghur houses."

Representatives of the Kokand Khanate played a significant role not only in trade, but also in the production of handicrafts in East Turkestan. In particular, the Andijan people played an important role in the Turfan handicrafts of the Dungan, Chinese, Andijan, Kashgar and York peoples. The Turfans themselves were less engaged in handicrafts.

Kokand traders brought to Central Turkestan mainly silk, cotton and wool fabrics from the products of the Central Asian khanates. Silk and semi-silk fabrics produced at the Kokand and Margilan factories are among the main commodities in the Kashgar and Yorkend markets. It should be noted that 81% of the fabric woven mainly in Kashgar was sent to Central Asia [4.S.158]. Although silk and semi-silk fabrics were also produced in East Turkestan, their quality was not very high.

Writing about fabric sales in East Turkestan markets, Ch. Valikhanov brought a lot of silk and semi-silk fabrics from Kokand khanate to Kashgar, and a small amount of cotton fabrics. Because cotton fabrics were cheap in East Turkestan, khanate traders did not benefit from it. The Kokand merchant, who brought cloth from the khanate, earned an average of 2 gold coins, [3.B.78]. Popular among the people of East Turkestan and the Kyrgyz, the woolen felt woven in Namangan, called "Timpai"

or "black helmet", is highly valued for its toughness, durability and. In Namangan, two pieces of it were valued at 12-16 tenge, while the Kyrgyz exchanged it for 5 sheep. In Yorkend, a simple coat made of timpai cost 0.5 gold [6.S.76].

The goods brought from Kashgar to the Kokand khanate were varied. In Kashgar, woven felt, bed linen, and polos were exported to Central Asia. Kashgar sandstones processed by blacksmiths and carvers are considered to be the most popular in Fergana. Kashgar and Aksu blacksmiths made their products from copper, iron and cast iron. These products are mostly exported to Russia and China.

Kokand traders have also benefited greatly from products made in China. Tea has a special place among them. In particular, the annual turnover of tea products was 30,000 pounds and was loaded on 30,000 horses [4.S.124].

Kokand traders traded in East Turkestan through barter or Kokand's gold, silver, and copper coins, as well as coins minted in East Turkestan itself.

From the above information it can be concluded that:

After the Manchu government invaded East Turkestan, the country banned local Uighur traders from trading in Central Asia, including the Kokand Khanate, in order to stop external influences.

As a result, after Kokand traders were allowed to trade in East Turkestan markets, they entered East Turkestan and expanded their trading activities in the country.

Chinese products, such as tea, silk, ravocho, silver yombs, and local fabrics, were purchased from Chinese and Uyghur traders and exported to Central Asian khanates, Kyrgyz and Kazakhs, Russia, Afghanistan, and the Middle East. They monopolized trade in East Turkestan.

The Kokand traders gathered in the most important cities of East Turkestan and began to form their own associations to be legally protected before the local and Chinese governments. Farmers and artisans from the khanate also came here and engaged in their activities. They enriched these spheres of economic life of East Turkestan with the agricultural culture and handicraft traditions of their country, and they themselves assimilated the achievements of East Turkestan people in economic life.

A system of elders-gods appointed by the Kokand khan was established to control traders, farmers and artisans who were citizens of the Kokand khanate in East Turkestan.

By the middle of the 19th century, the main goods in trade between the two countries were Chinese and Russian goods. However, local goods were also common in trade between the Kokand Khanate and East Turkestan.

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